

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 2, Выпуск 2, 29 Февраль

CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, MODERN DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT METHODS OF HEMANGIOMA IN CHILDREN

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Annotatsiya: In this article, special attention is paid to highlighting the factors causing hemangioma, pathogenesis, specific clinical symptoms, important diagnostic factors in the diagnosis of the disease, and modern principles of treatment.

Key words: hemangioma, etiology, types (simple (capillary), cavernous, combined, mixed), diagnosis, treatment

Hemangioma is a benign vascular formation that occurs due to an embryonic disorder in the development of blood vessels. A tumor appears on any part of the skin and looks like a red, purple or bluish point raised from the surface of the skin. It is often detected at birth or formed in the first weeks of life. Treatment is surgical and conservative.

Hemangioma appears in children at birth. This change is the result of vascular malformation. The detection rate of hemangioma in newborns reaches 3%. In 10% of cases, the problem is detected in the first year of the child's life. Statistics show that this is the most common soft tissue tumor in pediatrics. The detection rate reaches 50% of cases. In girls, the problem occurs 3-5 times more often. Hemangioma in adults manifests itself in exceptional cases with improper treatment in childhood.

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Hemangioma is a good-quality tumor that develops quickly. It grows rapidly on the surface and deep within the skin. As the defect grows, it can destroy surrounding tissue and cause vision, hearing, and breathing problems. When a hemangioma is damaged, there is a risk of infection and ulcerated deformations may appear on the surface.

The causes of hemangioma are not fully understood. It was found that the pathology is the result of changes in the formation of the vascular system at the embryonic stage. The following factors can affect this process:

- when a pregnant woman takes certain medications;
- past viral diseases;
- adverse environmental conditions.

Since hemangioma on the skin is most often detected in girls, there is a connection between swelling and hormonal regulation, but this is not the main factor.

The main types of the disease and clinical symptoms:

Depending on the morphological characteristics, the following types of hemangiomas are distinguished:

- simple (capillary). It has clear borders, has a red or purple-blue color. When pressed, it turns pale, then regains its color;
- cavernous — lumpy, nodular formation located under the skin. It is characterized by a soft elastic consistency, which is explained by the structure - inside there are spaces filled with blood;
- combined — It has a skin and a subcutaneous part. Clinical manifestations are characteristic of capillary and cavernous type;
- mixed — a tumor with a complex structure, including elements of vascular, nervous, connective and lymphoid tissues. Color, consistency and appearance will vary depending on the elements included.

Tumors are single and multiple in nature and can be small or large. In pediatrics, simple forms are diagnosed in 95% of cases. Symptoms of hemangioma are manifested only externally, rarely the patient complains of itching and discomfort in the affected area.

Treatment and examination of a child with hemangioma provides:

- Pediatrician
- Surgeon
- Dermatologist

In addition, consultation with an ophthalmologist, otorhinolaryngologist, urologist, dentist and pediatric gynecologist is indicated. An ultrasound examination of the affected

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area is performed to determine the depth of spread and assess the structure. The complex evaluates the speed of blood flow in the tumor itself and in the vessels that supply it.

There will be no discomfort for patients. The tumor may regress on its own. It is not necessary to eliminate soft tissue tumors that do not have indications for surgical removal. The decision on the treatment scheme or dynamic control method is always made by the doctor.

In the past, when a hemangioma was diagnosed in childhood, a wait-and-see approach was adopted, with doctors hoping that the tumor would resolve on its own before adulthood. Over time, this conclusion became irrelevant. In only 5% of cases, hemangioma in children disappears from the skin without consequences, in 2% of cases this happens before the age of 5.

Today, hemangioma is treated using the following methods:

- physical removal;
- surgical resection;
- drug therapy.

A list of the most commonly used physical removal methods includes: cryodestruction, laser radiation, sclerotherapy, and electrocoagulation. The described methods allow painless removal of soft tissue tumors. Complete disappearance lasts from several months to several years. Scars may remain on the skin.

In modern practice, the surgical method is rarely used. It is used for small hemangioma in adult patients. Tumors that are often located in invisible areas of the body are cut. The cosmetic effect is doubtful, scars remain on the surface of the skin.

Therapy based on the use of hormonal and antitumor drugs:

It is often used in the preparatory phase to reduce the hemangioma area. Due to drug therapy, complete resorption occurs rarely, in less than 2% of cases.

If it is not treated correctly and on time, complications that threaten human life and health may occur:

- germination with subsequent destruction of nearby organs;
- destruction of bone and muscle tissue;
- spinal cord compression;
- wound, infection of the tumor;
- malignancy;
- development of pathologies of the vascular system;
- cosmetic defect.

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Surgical removal of hemangiomas is not always necessary. The tumor may regress on its own. There are several stages in the extinction process. It begins with the appearance of a pale spot in the center of the tumor, then the shade changes and becomes normal towards the periphery. The process of disappearance can last for a long time, up to several years.

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